

THE MEDIATING EFFECT OF COLLABORATIVE LEARNING ON THE ATTITUDE TOWARD LEARNING SCIENCE AND MOTIVATION AMONG JUNIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS

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The Mediating Effect of Collaborative Learning on the Attitude toward Learning Science and Motivation among Junior High School Students

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Abstract

Student motivation in learning science remains a global concern, influencing academic performance and engagement. This quantitative study investigates the mediating effect of collaborative learning on the relationship between attitude toward learning science and motivation among junior high school students. Using a descriptive-correlational research design with mediation analysis, data were collected from 235 randomly selected students in a public junior high school in Davao City through standardized questionnaires on attitudes toward science, learning motivation, and collaborative learning, all validated for reliability. Results showed that students demonstrated a positive attitude toward science ($M = 3.67$), high learning motivation ($M = 4.04$), and very high engagement in collaborative learning ($M = 4.26$). Correlation analysis revealed strong positive relationships between attitude toward science and learning motivation ($r = 0.559, p < .001$), as well as between collaborative learning and learning motivation ($r = 0.599, p < .001$). Mediation analysis confirmed that collaborative learning significantly and partially mediated the relationship between attitude toward learning science and motivation, accounting for 31.4% of the total effect. These findings highlight the importance of fostering collaborative learning environments to enhance student motivation in science education. Educators are encouraged to integrate structured collaborative learning strategies to promote engagement and positive attitudes. Future research should explore the long-term impact of collaborative learning in different educational contexts to further optimize its benefits. The study contributes to the growing body of knowledge supporting collaborative learning as a key factor in improving science motivation and learning outcomes among junior high school students.

Keywords: *mediating effect of collaborative learning, attitude toward learning science, motivation among junior high school students*

Introduction

Keeping students motivated in learning is a global problem (Uriarte-Portillo et al., 2023). Fostering student interest is a core educational objective, yet research consistently demonstrates a troubling decline in student motivation for science throughout secondary school (Steidtmann et al., 2023). This highlights the growing importance of research on student learning motivation, which has received much attention rightfully (Ishida & Sekiyama, 2024).

In Tanzania, research highlights a major contextual challenge to student motivation in secondary schools (Mkimbili & Odegaard, 2019). A study from Onesia indicates that student learning motivation is significantly low (Kemal et al., 2023). In the United States, a study on American students highlighted a drop in motivation and enthusiasm toward learning science among high school students (Steidtmann et al., 2023).

Meanwhile, in the Philippines, echoing concerns in other countries facing science education challenges, reports indicate a lack of student motivation to learn (Briones et al., 2022). Supporting this point, a study in General Santos City found that students' motivation to learn is low (Mukhtar et al., 2020).

A lack of motivation can cultivate negative attitudes toward science, leading students to view it as irrelevant or difficult (Abd-El-Khalik & BouJaoude, 2019). This lack of motivation can further translate into low academic achievement, particularly within lecture-based learning environments (Hidajat et al., 2023). It is in this context that this study is considered urgent. Amidst this urgency, relevant research is scarce. Hence, this study is conducted.

Research Questions

This study aimed to ascertain how collaborative learning influenced junior high school students' attitudes and motivation to learn science. Specifically, this study aimed to obtain the following objectives:

1. How may the levels of collaborative learning be described in terms of:
 - 1.1. academic benefits;
 - 1.2. social benefits;
 - 1.3. generic skills; and
 - 1.4. continuing use of collaborative learning?
2. How may the levels of attitude toward learning science be described in terms of:
 - 2.1. attitude toward science teachers;
 - 2.2. anxiety in science;

- 2.3. enjoyment in science; and
- 2.4. science in society?
3. How may the levels of attitude toward learning science be described in terms of:
 - 3.1. intrinsic motivation;
 - 3.2. career motivation;
 - 3.3. self-determination;
 - 3.4. self-efficacy; and
 - 3.5. grade motivation?
4. Is there a significance of the relationship between collaborative learning, attitude toward learning science, and learning motivation among junior high school students in learning science?
5. Is there a significance of the mediating effect of collaborative learning on the relationship between attitude toward learning science and learning motivation among junior high school students?

Methodology

Research Design

Descriptive- correlational and mediation analyses. Non-experiment designs are observational, examining pre-existing relationships among variables without intervention. The descriptive correlational approach was utilized to characterize the variables of interest by exploring their behavioral, cognitive, environmental, and other relevant aspects. Correlation analysis, a statistical technique, was employed to identify associations and patterns among the measured variables (Chen & Wang, 2022). Furthermore, following Hayes (2018), mediation analysis was conducted to explore the influence of a third variable (the mediator) in the relationship between an independent and a dependent variable. This research specifically investigated the mediating role of collaborative learning in the connection between learning motivation and science learning attitudes among junior high school students, examining specific indicators within each variable.

Respondents

This study was conducted in selected public junior high schools of Cluster 3 in the Division of Davao City, Region XI, with 235 junior high school students participating. The research locale was chosen due to its potential to exhibit common challenges in science education, such as declining student interest or motivation in science subjects. Moreover, it has a diverse student body closely resembling the research target population, including students from various socioeconomic backgrounds and academic levels, making the findings more generalizable. The locale was also easily accessible for data collection and analysis. A uniform stratified random sampling method was employed to ensure representation across the junior high school population, minimizing potential bias. This technique is particularly well-suited for correlational studies investigating relationships between variables, as it strengthens the validity of findings (Olsen & Vasquez-Rossi, 2023). The sample size was determined using Raosoft software, drawn from a total population of 600 students, ensuring adequacy based on Rahman's (2023) recommendation that at least 100–150 participants are appropriate for larger populations in correlational studies. To maintain the study's reliability, only students enrolled in regular classes during the 2024-2025 school year who provided consent and assent were included. Students in special education programs with individualized learning plans, students not currently enrolled, and those who did not provide consent and assent were excluded to control for potential confounding variables.

Instrument

The researcher utilized a standardized questionnaire adapted and modified from three variables from the theoretical framework anchored with the Social Cognitive Theory (Bandura, 1986). To assess students' attitudes toward science (independent variable), a modified version of the Attitudes Towards Science Inventory Questionnaire (Gogolin & Swartz, 1992) was used. Learning motivation (dependent variable) was measured using a modified version of the Science Motivation Questionnaire (Glynn, Brickman, Armstrong & Taasobshirazi, 2011). Students' Views on the Collaborative Learning Questionnaire (Brown, 2007) was adapted and utilized for the mediating variable. The survey questionnaires mentioned were subject to research validation, pilot testing, and reliability tests.

The researcher measured the attitude toward science, and a questionnaire was adapted and modified from the study (Gogolin & Swartz, 1992). The Attitude Toward Science Inventory is a 36-item inventory with high construct validity. The Attitude Toward Science Inventory contains four indicators: (4) (1) attitudes toward science teachers, (2) anxiety in science, (3) enjoyment of science, and (4) views of science in society. This questionnaire was utilized to test the attitude toward learning science among junior high school students. When assessing the questionnaire, the respondents used the following criteria: 1 for very low, 2 for low, 3 for moderate, 4 for high, and 5 for very high. The outcome was analyzed using the Likert scale below. The overall reliability test result of attitude toward learning science which is the independent variable is 0.640 indicating that items were acceptable.

Also, the researcher measured the level of learning motivation in science, and a questionnaire was adapted and modified from the study of Glynn, Brickman, Armstrong, and Taasobshirazi (2011). The Science Motivation Questionnaire II consists of 25 items of declarative statements that are divided into five (5) levels of indicators: (1) intrinsic motivation, (2) career motivation, (3) self-

determination, (4) self-efficacy, and (5) grade Motivation. This questionnaire was utilized to test the level of learning motivation in the science of Junior High School students. When assessing the questionnaire, the respondents used the following criteria: 1 for very low, 2 for low, 3 for moderate, 4 for high, and 5 for very high. The outcome was analyzed using the Likert scale. The overall reliability test result of learning motivation in science among junior high school students which is the dependent variable is 0.897 indicating that items were very good.

Moreover, the mediating factor that influences learning motivation and attitude toward science is collaborative learning—the Students' views on the Collaborative Learning Questionnaire (Brown, 2007). The instrument consists of a 20-item test and has six (6) indicators: (1) Academic Benefits, (2) Social Benefits, (3) Generic Skills, (4) Negative Aspects, (5) Continuing using collaborative learning, and (6) Four people per group (max). The 5-point Likert Scale below was used to describe the data obtained in the study. The overall reliability test result of collaborative learning which is the mediating variable is 0.933 indicating that items were excellent.

Procedure

Following ethical review and approval by the Society for Moral Integrity and Legal Ethics (SMILE) Committee, the researcher obtained an endorsement letter from the Dean of the Graduate School of Holy Cross of Davao College to facilitate data collection. This endorsement and a separate notification letter were then submitted to participating school administrators, formally requesting permission to administer questionnaires to selected teacher respondents. A letter of intent was subsequently submitted to the Public Schools District Supervisor of Cluster 3, Davao City Division, through the Schools Division Superintendent, requesting approval to conduct the study within the division.

Before data collection, participants were provided with consent and assent forms, ensuring ethical practices. Upon receiving signed consent and assent, questionnaires were distributed to the student respondents, emphasizing the importance of honest responses.

Collected questionnaires were organized and prepared for analysis. The data was submitted to a statistician for processing and statistical analysis. The resulting statistical output was subsequently reviewed and interpreted to draw conclusions and insights relevant to the research.

Ethical Considerations

An important ethical consideration in this study is the potential psychological risk and the possibility of loss of confidentiality, as the study's respondents are minors. A series of measures were implemented to mitigate the risks. The researcher adhered to strict procedures to protect participants' well-being and privacy. Participants and their guardians received age-appropriate information about the study's goals and methods via consent and assent forms, emphasizing the voluntary nature of participation. The survey was designed to minimize potential distress, avoiding questions that may cause discomfort or anxiety. If any questions are considered sensitive for them, respondents could skip them without consequence. As the consent and assent forms explained, participants could leave the study without consequence. This ensured their autonomy and comfort throughout the research. Data was anonymized and securely stored to maintain confidentiality and prevent unauthorized access. These measures protected participant rights and well-being, creating a safe research environment and minimizing potential risks.

Results and Discussion

Descriptive Analysis

Table 1. *Descriptive Table*

<i>Variable</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Descriptive Level</i>
Attitude Toward Learning Science	3.67	0.269	High
Perception on the Science Teacher	4.23	0.472	Very High
Anxiety in Science	2.41	0.790	High
Enjoyment in Science	3.91	0.549	High
Science in Society	4.14	0.462	High
Learning Motivation	4.04	0.480	High
Intrinsic Motivation	4.02	0.605	High
Career Motivation	3.88	0.734	High
Self-Determination	3.98	0.564	High
Self-Efficacy	3.89	0.656	High
Grade Motivation	4.29	0.630	Very High
Collaborative Learning	4.26	0.437	Very High
Academic Benefits	4.26	0.478	Very High
Social Benefits	4.21	0.596	Very High
Generic Skills	4.23	0.485	Very High
Continuing using collaborative learning	4.34	0.515	Very High

Legend: 4.20-5.00, Very High; 3.40-4.19, High; 2.60-3.39, Moderate; 1.80-2.59, Low; 1.00-1.79, Very Low

Junior high school students generally exhibit a positive attitude toward science learning, as indicated by an average score of 3.67, reflecting a "very good" perception. Their strongest regard is for their science teachers ($M = 4.23$), with a high level of agreement on the relevance of science in society ($M = 4.14$). Enjoyment in science is also rated highly ($M = 3.91$), though some students experience anxiety ($M = 2.41$), with noticeable individual differences in its intensity. Despite this, their overall attitude toward science remains favorable, demonstrating consistency in responses and highlighting an appreciation for science education.

Students also display strong motivation for learning science ($M = 4.04$), particularly in academic performance ($M = 4.29$) and intrinsic motivation ($M = 4.02$). Collaborative learning is rated very highly ($M = 4.26$), with students showing strong support for its continuation ($M = 4.34$) and recognizing its academic and skill-building benefits. Social benefits receive slightly lower ratings ($M = 4.21$), reflecting more varied opinions. While concerns about anxiety and career motivation persist, the findings indicate that collaborative and motivational strategies effectively enhance student engagement and learning in science.

This study investigated the interconnectedness of student attitudes toward science, motivation, and collaborative learning engagement, specifically within science education for junior high school students. The findings revealed a generally positive attitude toward science learning among these students, echoing the moderate positive correlation between science attitudes and academic achievement reported by Liou et al. (2021). However, this contrasts with the findings of Sahin and Yilmaz (2020), who observed a decrease in science interest during adolescence, possibly attributable to variations in pedagogical approaches and cultural backgrounds. Consistent with Ajzen's (1991) Theory of Planned Behavior, a positive science attitude can foster engagement and persistence, although factors like teaching effectiveness and resource availability also play a role. This observation supports contemporary educational trends emphasizing student-centered learning, such as inquiry-based learning and real-world applications, to maintain student interest and improve academic outcomes. The study emphasizes the need to capitalize on students' science enthusiasm to promote sustained engagement and encourage future STEM careers, offering valuable implications for educators and policymakers.

Junior high school students demonstrate a strong inclination towards science learning, consistently showing positive attitudes that create a promising setting for effective teaching methods. This observation aligns with research by Liou et al. (2021), which found a correlation between student attitudes and science achievement, indicating that motivation can lead to improved learning results. However, it is important to note that high motivation does not always translate to high academic performance, as Salta and Koulougliotis (2020) highlighted. They emphasized the importance of other factors, such as teaching quality, available resources, and individual learning styles, in achieving academic success. To capitalize on students' enthusiasm, educators can utilize active learning strategies like collaborative projects and inquiry-based learning, which can help foster deeper comprehension and critical thinking abilities.

The findings reveal a high level of collaborative learning in science among junior high school students, showcasing consistent engagement in group-based activities that enhance critical thinking, problem-solving, and interpersonal skills, as Gillies (2020) emphasized. This highlights the positive impact of collaboration on both academic and social development. To sustain and maximize these benefits, educators are encouraged to implement structured group tasks that promote interdependence and accountability while addressing challenges like unequal participation, as noted by Chiong and Jovanovic (2022). However, limitations such as dominance, conflict, and disengagement, highlighted by Johnson and Johnson (2021), underscore the need for thoughtful planning, precise role definitions, and continuous group dynamics monitoring. This study confirms that collaborative learning is essential for successful science education. It also highlights the need for strategies to overcome the challenges it presents for learners with diverse needs.

Correlation Analysis

Table 2. Correlation Table

Variable	R	p-value	Decision on Ho
Attitude toward Learning Science	0.392	0.000	Reject Ho
Collaborative Learning	0.599	0.000	Reject Ho
Learning Motivation	0.559	0.000	Reject Ho

This study highlights significant relationships between students' attitudes toward science, collaborative learning practices, and learning motivation. A moderate positive correlation ($r = 0.392$, $p < 0.05$) was found between students' attitudes toward science and their engagement in collaborative learning, suggesting that those with more favorable views of science are more active in collaborative learning. Additionally, a strong positive correlation ($r = 0.599$, $p < 0.05$) between collaborative learning and motivation indicates that participation in group activities enhances students' drive to learn. Similarly, a strong correlation ($r = 0.559$, $p < 0.05$) between attitudes toward science and motivation implies that a positive perception of science fosters greater enthusiasm for learning. Given the statistical significance of these relationships, fostering positive attitudes toward science and encouraging collaborative learning can effectively enhance student motivation, engagement, and academic performance.

The study found a moderately strong positive correlation between students' attitudes toward science and participation in collaborative learning. This suggests that students with a more positive view of science are likelier to thrive in group learning environments. This aligns with research emphasizing the role of positive attitudes in enhancing participation and fostering better learning and social outcomes in collaborative settings (Slavin, 2021). The results highlight the importance of cultivating positive attitudes through

strategies like inquiry-based learning and real-world applications, which can, in turn, promote collaboration (García & Morales, 2022). However, regardless of attitudes, group dynamics, and uneven contributions may hinder collaboration (Zhang & Li, 2023). To address this, educators should design structured collaborative frameworks with clear roles and accountability to ensure equitable participation, offering valuable insights for improving science education practices.

Research has demonstrated a strong correlation between collaborative learning and learning motivation among junior high school students. Students who participate in collaborative activities tend to be more motivated to learn. This finding is consistent with prior studies, such as the work of Slavin (2021), which suggested that collaborative learning can boost intrinsic motivation by encouraging peer interaction and developing shared objectives. The results and score the potential benefits of incorporating collaborative learning strategies into classroom settings to foster motivation, a notion further supported by the research of García and Morales (2022). However, challenges such as poorly structured tasks, unequal participation, and students' social anxieties may hinder collaboration effectiveness, as Zhang and Li (2023) noted. Therefore, educators need to carefully design collaborative tasks, ensure equitable contributions, and support effective teamwork to maximize the benefits of collaborative learning and motivation.

The findings show a strong positive relationship between students' attitudes toward learning science and their learning motivation, suggesting that a favorable attitude toward science can significantly enhance students' motivation to engage in the subject. This aligns with Salta and Koulougliotis (2021), who found that positive attitudes toward science are linked with greater motivation and persistence. The implications for educators are clear: cultivating a positive attitude through engaging, inquiry-based strategies, such as hands-on experiments and real-world applications, can enhance student motivation. However, other actors, such as classroom environment, teaching quality, and individual learning needs, should also be considered, as noted by Chou and Tsai (2023), to create a comprehensive learning environment that supports motivation and engagement.

Mediation Analysis

Table 3. *Mediation Table*

Type	Effect	Estimate	SE	B	Z	P
Indirect	ATLS \Rightarrow CL \Rightarrow LM	0.313	0.0597	0.18	5.24	< .001
Component	ATLS \Rightarrow CL	0.637	0.0975	0.39	6.53	< .001
	CL \Rightarrow LM	0.492	0.0559	0.45	8.79	< .001
Direct	ATLS \Rightarrow LM	0.684	0.0909	0.38	7.52	< .001
Total	ATLS \Rightarrow LM	0.997	0.0966	0.56	10.32	< .001

Percent of Mediation = 31.4%

Figure 1. *Path Model Illustrates the Mediation of Collaborative Learning (CL) in the Relationship Between Attitude Toward Learning Science (ATLS) and Learning Motivation (LM)*

In Table 3, analysis of Junior high school students' Attitudes toward Learning Science (ATLS), Collaborative Learning (CL), and Learning Motivation (LM) revealed significant relationships. A statistically significant indirect effect (estimate = 0.313, $p < .001$) was observed, indicating that Collaborative Learning mediates the relationship between ATLS and LM (ATLS \Rightarrow CL \Rightarrow LM). Specifically, collaborative Learning explains a portion of how ATLS influences LM. The direct effect of ATLS on LM (ATLS \Rightarrow LM) was also significant (estimate = 0.684, $\beta = 0.38$, $p < .001$). The presence of both significant direct and indirect effects suggest partial mediation. This means that ATLS influences LM both directly and indirectly through Collaborative Learning.

The mediation analysis indicated that 31.4% of the total effect of ATLS on LM occurs through Collaborative Learning, while the direct effect accounts for the remaining 68.6%. These results emphasize the role of Collaborative Learning in understanding the complex

relationship between ATLS and LM, demonstrating the importance of considering both direct and mediated pathways when examining student learning motivation.

The mediation model above examines the influence of Attitude Toward Learning Science (ATLS) on Learning Motivation (LM) through Collaborative Learning (CL). The model reveals a strong positive relationship between ATLS and CL, with a path coefficient of 0.64. This suggests that students with more positive attitudes toward science learning are more involved in collaborative learning activities. Furthermore, the t-path coefficient from CL to LM is 0.49, indicating that participation in collaborative learning significantly contributes to increased learning motivation. These findings underscore the potential mediating role of CL in the relationship between ATLS and LM.

In addition to the indirect effect through CL, ATLS has a significant direct effect on LM, with a coefficient of 0.68. This indicates that a positive attitude toward learning science independently contributes to increased learning motivation, even without the influence of collaborative learning. Together, the model shows partial mediation, where the direct effect of ATLS on LM and the indirect effect through CL are significant. This emphasizes the importance of fostering positive attitudes toward learning science and incorporating collaborative learning strategies to optimize students' motivation. The findings underline the need to create learning environments supporting individual attitudes and group-based interactions to enhance educational outcomes.

Conclusions

This study demonstrated that collaborative learning significantly mediates the relationship between attitude toward learning science and learning motivation among junior high school students. The findings confirm that students with a positive attitude toward science are more likely to be motivated to learn when engaged in collaborative learning environments. This supports Bandura's Social Cognitive Theory, emphasizing the role of social interactions in shaping motivation and behavior. The mediation analysis revealed that 31.4% of the total effect of attitude toward learning science on learning motivation is explained through collaborative learning, highlighting its critical role in fostering student engagement. Furthermore, these findings align with the goals of Sustainable Development Goal 4 (SDG 4) by promoting inclusive and equitable education through active, student-centered learning approaches. Given these findings, it is recommended that educators integrate structured collaborative learning strategies into science curricula to enhance student engagement, motivation, and learning outcomes. School administrators should support professional development programs that train teachers in implementing effective collaborative learning techniques. Policymakers should prioritize education reforms that incorporate collaborative learning as a fundamental teaching approach. Additionally, future research should explore the long-term impact of collaborative learning across different educational contexts, investigate its effects on diverse student populations, and examine additional mediating factors that may influence student motivation. By reinforcing the role of collaborative learning in science education, this study contributes to a growing body of evidence advocating for innovative teaching strategies that foster student motivation, engagement, and academic success.

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